

1 **Appendix**

2 Complete code with virtual data for probability- and favourability-based SDMs:

3 <https://github.com/elisamarchetto/Favourability-Probability>

4 **Tables**

5

RANDOM SAMPLING

MODEL	TEST	FAVOURABILITY	PROBABILITY
GLM	chi-squared	631.912 (p-value <0.001)	396401.700 (p-value <0.001)
GAM	chi-squared	225.600 (p-value <0.001)	115436.000 (p-value <0.001)
RF	chi-squared	2588.089 (p-value <0.001)	144298.500 (p-value <0.001)
BRT	chi-squared	29368.390 (p-value <0.001)	238044.100 (p-value <0.001)

Table 1: p-values and chi-squared values of Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test. The test was carried out on the favourability-based and probability-based predictions of 50 virtual species estimated using a random sampling of presence/absence points comparing the sample prevalence groups.

STRATIFIED SAMPLING

MODEL	TEST	FAVOURABILITY	PROBABILITY
GLM	chi-squared	433.493 (p-value <0.001)	367401.200 (p-value <0.001)
GAM	chi-squared	275.230 (p-value <0.001)	118533.600 (p-value <0.001)
RF	chi-squared	3201.369 (p-value <0.001)	146264.600 (p-value <0.001)
BRT	chi-squared	13729.390 (p-value <0.001)	217202.200 (p-value <0.001)

Table 2: p-values and chi-squared values of Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test. The test was carried out on the favourability-based and probability-based predictions of 50 virtual species estimated using a stratified sampling of presence/absence points comparing the sample prevalence groups.

GLM

comparison	Z test statistic	adjusted p-value
F0.2R - F0.2S	-10.501	3.829×10^{-24}
F0.4R - F0.4S	-10.020	5.604×10^{-22}
F0.5R - F0.5S	-10.521	3.098×10^{-24}
F0.6R - F0.6S	-10.714	3.930×10^{-25}
F0.8R - F0.8S	-10.457	6.156×10^{-24}
P0.2R - P0.2S	-10.641	8.655×10^{-25}
P0.4R - P0.4S	-9.948	1.156×10^{-21}
P0.5R - P0.5S	-10.213	7.806×10^{-23}
P0.6R - P0.6S	-10.344	1.998×10^{-23}
P0.8R - P0.8S	-9.652	2.169×10^{-20}

Table 3: p-values and Z values of Dunn's test computed for GLM. According to the pairwise comparisons, "F" indicates favourability, "P" probability, "R" random sampling and "S" stratified sampling, while the decimal number is referred to the sample prevalence.

GAM

comparison	Z test statistic	adjusted p-value
F0.2R - F0.2S	-16.169	3.769×10^{-57}
F0.4R - F0.4S	-15.604	3.063×10^{-53}
F0.5R - F0.5S	-16.311	3.693×10^{-58}
F0.6R - F0.6S	-16.194	2.506×10^{-57}
F0.8R - F0.8S	15.612	2.727×10^{-53}
P0.2R - P0.2S	-15.656	1.355×10^{-53}
P0.4R - P0.4S	-15.521	1.131×10^{-52}
P0.5R - P0.5S	-16.224	1.540×10^{-57}
P0.6R - P0.6S	-16.088	1.385×10^{-56}
P0.8R - P0.8S	-15.493	1.742×10^{-52}

Table 4: p-values and Z values of Dunn's test computed for GAM. According to the pairwise comparisons, "F" indicates favourability, "P" probability, "R" random sampling and "S" stratified sampling, while the decimal number is referred to the sample prevalence.

RF

comparison	Z test statistic	adjusted p-value
F0.2R - F0.2S	-12.601	9.383×10^{-35}
F0.4R - F0.4S	-12.752	1.361×10^{-35}
F0.5R - F0.5S	-13.432	1.761×10^{-39}
F0.6R - F0.6S	-13.980	9.343×10^{-43}
F0.8R - F0.8S	-13.467	1.100×10^{-39}
P0.2R - P0.2S	-12.494	3.602×10^{-34}
P0.4R - P0.4S	-12.696	2.799×10^{-35}
P0.5R - P0.5S	-13.345	5.704×10^{-39}
P0.6R - P0.6S	-13.911	2.431×10^{-42}
P0.8R - P0.8S	-13.332	6.744×10^{-39}

Table 5: p-values and Z values of Dunn's test computed for RF. According to the pairwise comparisons, "F" indicates favourability, "P" probability, "R" random sampling and "S" stratified sampling, while the decimal number is referred to the sample prevalence.

BRT

comparison	Z test statistic	adjusted p-value
F0.2R - F0.2S	-11.616	1.536×10^{-29}
F0.4R - F0.4S	-13.220	3.011×10^{-38}
F0.5R - F0.5S	-13.814	9.383×10^{-42}
F0.6R - F0.6S	-14.413	1.934×10^{-45}
F0.8R - F0.8S	-14.823	4.711×10^{-48}
P0.2R - P0.2S	-12.824	5.410×10^{-36}
P0.4R - P0.4S	-13.281	1.341×10^{-38}
P0.5R - P0.5S	-13.380	3.572×10^{-39}
P0.6R - P0.6S	-13.596	1.907×10^{-40}
P0.8R - P0.8S	-13.208	3.555×10^{-38}

Table 6: p-values and Z values of Dunn's test computed for BRT. According to the pairwise comparisons, "F" indicates favourability, "P" probability, "R" random sampling and "S" stratified sampling, while the decimal number is referred to the sample prevalence.

6 Figures

Figure 1: Pixels variabilities of mean probability and mean favourability predictions. The first column on the left shows the pixels variability of the mean probability of species occurrence calculated for GLM, RF, GAM and BRT, the central column, the pixels variability of the mean favourability of species occurrence calculated for GLM, RF, GAM and BRT and the right column the difference between the pixels variabilities of mean probability and mean favourability outcomes.

Figure 2: Distribution values of 50 virtual species between first and third quartiles within the range of prevalence values of the favourability and the probability predictions estimated with GLM. (A) favourability-based and probability-based species distribution values related to a random sampling of presence-absence points, (B) favourability-based and probability-based species distribution values related to a stratified sampling of presence-absence points. The mean value is represented with * symbol.

Figure 3: Distribution values of 50 virtual species between first and third quartiles within the range of prevalence values of the favourability and the probability predictions estimated with RF. (C) favourability-based and probability-based species distribution values related to a random sampling of presence-absence points, (D) favourability-based and probability-based species distribution values related to a stratified sampling of presence-absence points. The mean value is represented with * symbol.

Figure 4: Distribution values of 50 virtual species between first and third quartiles within the range of prevalence values of the favourability and the probability predictions estimated with GAM. **(E)** favourability-based and probability-based species distribution values related to a random sampling of presence-absence points, **(F)** favourability-based and probability-based species distribution values related to a stratified sampling of presence-absence points. The mean value is represented with * symbol.

Figure 5: Distribution values of 50 virtual species between first and third quartiles within the range of prevalence values of the favourability and the probability predictions estimated with BRT. (**G**) favourability-based and probability-based species distribution values related to a random sampling of presence-absence points, (**H**) favourability-based and probability-based species distribution values related to a stratified sampling of presence-absence points. The mean value is represented with * symbol.

Figure 6: Distribution values between first and third quartiles of AUCs related to GLM within the range of sample prevalence. The first distribution (**A**) is referred to the random sampling method, the second distribution (**B**) is referred to the stratified sampling method. The mean value is represented with * symbol.

Figure 7: Distribution values between first and third quartiles of AUCs related to RF within the range of sample prevalence. The first distribution (**C**) is referred to the random sampling method, the second distribution (**D**) is referred to the stratified sampling method. The mean value is represented with * symbol.

Figure 8: Distribution values between first and third quartiles of AUCs related to GAM within the range of sample prevalence. The first distribution (**E**) is referred to the random sampling method, the second distribution (**F**) is referred to the stratified sampling method. The mean value is represented with * symbol.

Figure 9: Distribution values between first and third quartiles of AUCs related to BRT within the range of sample prevalence. The first distribution (**G**) is referred to the random sampling method, the second distribution (**H**) is referred to the stratified sampling method. The mean value is represented with * symbol.

7 REAL SPECIES SCENARIO

8

9 We analyzed the tendency of favourability to reduce the variability of the predictions
10 across different degrees of sample prevalence in juxtaposition with the suitability
11 outcomes for two real species that share part of their geographic distribution (Fig. 9).
12 Since the real absences were not provided we could infer only the habitat suitability
13 and we could not estimate the actual probability of occurrence.

14 However, the study focused on the calculation of the coefficients of variations of *Picea*
15 *abies* and *Fagus sylvatica*.

16 The species occurrences in Italy of *Picea abies* and *Fagus sylvatica* were selected from
17 EU-Forest (Mauri et al., 2017), a dataset of European tree species distribution (<http://dx.doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.c.3288407>) that blends forest plot surveys
18 from National Forest Inventories on an INSPIRE-compliant 1km × 1km grid.
19

20 We randomly sampled 1000 presence and pseudo-absence points in order to fulfill the
21 sequence of sample prevalence values (i.e., 0.2, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.8) and we randomly
22 subsampled 5 replicates of the 19 bioclimatic variables with 10 arc-minutes of spatial
23 resolution which were also used as predictors. Suitability and favorability models
24 for each prevalence values were estimated using the generalized linear model. The
25 favourability predictions variability of *Picea abies* and *Fagus sylvatica* proved to be
26 more stable across the degrees of sample prevalence than the suitability outcomes
27 (Fig. 10), (Fig. 11) demonstrating that comparisons of species distributions of real
28 species are more reliable using the favourability models.

29 **References**

30 Mauri, A., Strona, G., San-Miguel-Ayanz, J (2017). EU-Forest, a high-
31 resolution tree occurrence dataset for Europe. *Sci Data* 4, 160123.
32 <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.123>

33 999

Figure 10: Habitat suitability of *Fagus sylvatica* and *Picea abies*. The first map on the left shows the suitability of *Fagus sylvatica*'s occurrence estimated using a random sampling of presences and pseudo-absences (sample prevalence value: 0.2), the second on the right represents the suitability of *Picea abies*'s occurrence estimated using a random sampling of presences and pseudo-absences (sample prevalence value: 0.2).

Figure 11: Predictions variability of *Fagus sylvatica* and *Picea abies*. The first column on the left represents the suitability-based predictions variability, calculated as Coefficient of Variation (CV) across the sample prevalence values of *Fagus sylvatica* and *Picea abies*, while, the second column shows the favourability-based predictions variability.

Figure 12: Distribution values of the difference between suitability-based coefficients of variation and favourability-based coefficients of variation for *Fagus sylvatica* and *Picea abies*. The median value is represented with * symbol.